

Method of Batch Production of Semiconductor Strain Transducer Elements. Patent SU, no. SU1259104A1

Abstract

The invention relates to a measurement technique and can be used in the manufacture of semiconductor integral sensors of mechanical quantities. The aim of the invention is to improve the accuracy of manufacturing semiconductor sensitive tenso-elements with predetermined calibration characteristics by choosing one of the tenso-elements as a control and measuring its high-performance parameter. To measure the output parameter of the control strain element 4, the substrate is placed on the support 5 and is loaded in the area of the control strain element 4 with a constant mechanical load. There is a pause in the pickling process for this. 2 hp f-1, 1 ill.

1 Description

(21) 3650805/25 – 28

(22) 11.10.83

(46) 23.09.86. Ehr.35

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(53) 531.781.2(088.8)

(56)

1. Ankudinov D.T., Mamaev K.N. Small-base strain gauges of resistance. - M.: Mashinostroenie, 1968, p. 52 – 53.
2. Vaganov V.I., Goncharova N.I. Control of profile thickness of elastic elements of integral mechanoelectric transducers. / In: Measuring transducers of mechanical and thermal quantities on the basis of microelectronics. M.: MDNT, 1980, p. 69 – 75.

(54) Method of Batch Production of Semiconductor Strain Transducer Elements.

(57) The invention relates to measuring equipment and can be used in the manufacture of semiconductor integrated sensors of mechanical quantities - displacements, forces, pressures, acceleration and other physical parameters.

A known method for group manufacturing of semiconductor sensitive elements is that a group of strain elements is formed on a wafer of single-crystal semiconductor material, the wafer is placed

in an etching bath and the surface layer is etched until the wafer breaks up into individual strain elements [1].

However, this method does not ensure the accuracy of making strain gauge elements in terms of thickness.

The closest to the invention in terms of technical essence and the result achieved is the method of group manufacturing of semiconductor sensitive strain cells, consisting in the fact that a group of strain cells is formed on a substrate, the substrate is placed in an etching bath and the surface layer is etched for a specified time [2].

The known method does not ensure the accuracy of manufacturing semiconductor strain-sensitive elements, since for the accurate manufacture of strain element it is necessary to take into account the deviation from the tolerance of not only the shape and dimensions of the elastic element, whose role is played by a substrate, but also the elasticity module of the substrate material, strain-sensitivity of semiconductor material and electrical resistance of strain element.

The goal of the invention is to improve the accuracy of semiconductor sensing strain gauge elements with given calibration characteristics.

The set goal is achieved by the fact that according to the method of group manufacture of sensitive semiconductor strain-gauge elements, consisting in the fact that a group of strain-gauge elements is formed on a substrate, the substrate is placed in an etching bath and the surface layer is etched, before etching to one of the tensocells, selected as a reference, connect lead wires, load the substrate in the location area of the tensocell by constant mechanical load and measure the output parameter of control in pauses of the etching process.

The substrate 1 of the original semiconductor material contains a group 2 of strain cells, a local membrane 3, a control strain cell 4 and a support 5.

The method is carried out as follows.

On the substrate 1 of the original semiconductor material a group 2 of strain gauge elements, such as single strain gauges, strain gauge half-bridges or bridges are formed. According to one variant of the method, the substrate is placed in a bath and the surface layer is etched in the area of the future location of the reference strain gauge. In this case, a local membrane 3 is formed on which a reference strain element 4 is placed. Strain cell 4 can be formed in the form of an integral strain

bridge, the resistors of which are placed on the areas of the largest deformations of the membrane 3.

After formation of strain-gauge elements to one of them, selected as a control, connect lead wires, structurally designed in the form of contact pads for connecting the probe head, set the substrate on the stand 5, load the substrate in the location of the control strain-gauge element 4 constant mechanical load (in the version with a depression - a concentrated force) and measure the output parameter of the control strain-gauge element 4, such as the resistance of a single tensoresistor, the output voltage of half-bridge or full.

Then the load is removed, the substrate 1 is placed in an etching bath and the substrate is etched. Periodically, during the etching process, pauses are arranged, the substrate is removed from the bath and the loading of the tensocell is repeated and its output parameter is measured. When the given value of this parameter is reached, etching is stopped. Use of the proposed method makes it possible to increase the accuracy of manufacturing of semiconductor sensitive strain elements with the given calibration characteristics. The share of strain gauge elements in the group, which is rejected due to too low sensitivity to the parameter measured by the strain gauge element, decreases. The dispersion of characteristics between the strain-gauge elements of different lots is considerably reduced. All this contributes to increasing the efficiency of the manufacturing process and reducing the cost of the products.

2 Claims

1. The method of group manufacturing of semiconductor sensitive strain cells, which consists in forming a group of strain cells on a substrate, placing the substrate in an etching bath and etching the surface layer, **WHICH IS CHARACTERIZED BY THE FACT THAT**, in order to improve accuracy, before etching, lead wires are connected to one of the test strain-gauge elements, the substrate is loaded with constant mechanical load in the location area of the strain-gauge element, and the input parameter of the test strain-gauge element is measured in pauses of the etching process.
2. Method according to clause 1, **WHICH IS CHARACTERIZED BY THE FACT THAT** beforehand in the substrate is etched a recess for placing the control strain-gauge, and the substrate is loaded with a concentrated force.
3. Method according to clauses 1, **WHICH IS CHARACTERIZED BY THE FACT THAT** the control strain element is formed in the form of an integral strain bridge.

3 Similar Documents

Publication	Publication Date	Title
US3927560A	1975 – 12 – 23	Moment desensitization of load cells
US4960177A	1990 – 10 – 02	Silicon membrane micro-scale
SU1259104A1	1986 – 09 – 23	Method of group production of ...
CA1178083 A	1984 – 11 – 20	Measuring ...
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SU960559A2	1982 – 09 – 23	Pressure sensor
GB2129565A	1984 – 05 – 16	Pressure and temperature transducer
SU1585722A1	1990 – 08 – 15	Method of predicting residual...
SU1247693A1	1986 – 07 – 30	Semiconductor measuring device
SU1303857A1	1987 – 04 – 15	Pressure measuring transducer
SU1583763A1	1990 – 08 – 07	Method of determining ...
SU1293474A1	1987 – 02 – 28	Method of manufacturing ...
SU1204976A1	1986 – 01 – 15	Method of measuring principal stresses
SU1415048A1	1988 – 08 – 07	Method of determining part ...
JPS59169183A	1984 – 09 – 25	Strain gauge type ...
RU 2110766C1	1998 – 05 – 10	Device...
SUT467383A1	1989 – 03 – 23	Strain-thermocouple
SU1201673A1	1985 – 12 – 30	Method of measuring thickness
SU566128A1	1977 – 07 – 25	Deformation sensor
Dibiet al.	2002	Combined effect of the membrane flatness defect ...
SU1302154A1	1987 – 04 – 07	Pressure sensor
SU974107A1	1982 – 11 – 15	Device for measuring residual ...
SU1224563A1	1986 – 04 – 15	Integrated strain transducer
SU1270541A1	1986 – 11 – 15	Method of determining residual ...

4 Priority And Related Applications

4.1 Priority Applications

Application	Priority date	Filing date	Title
SU833650805A	1983 – 10 – 11	1983-10-11	Method of Batch Production of ...

4.2 Applications Claiming Priority

Application	Filing date	Title
SU833650805A	1983 – 10 – 11	Method of Batch Production of Semiconductor...

СОЮЗ СОВЕТСКИХ
СОЦИАЛИСТИЧЕСКИХ
РЕСПУБЛИК

09 SU (U) 1259104 A1

(51)4 G 01 B 7/18

ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ КОМИТЕТ СССР
ПО ДЕЛАМ ИЗОБРЕТЕНИЙ И ОТКРЫТИЙ

ОПИСАНИЕ ИЗОБРЕТЕНИЯ К АВТОРСКОМУ СВИДЕТЕЛЬСТВУ

(21) 3650805/25-28

(22) 11.10.83

(46) 23.09.86. Бюл. № 35

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мерительные преобразователи механи-
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(54) СПОСОБ ГРУППОВОГО ИЗГОТОВЛЕНИЯ
ПОЛУПРОВОДНИКОВЫХ ЧУВСТВИТЕЛЬНЫХ
ТЕНЗОЭЛЕМЕНТОВ

(57) Изобретение относится к измери-
тельной технике и может использоваться
при изготовлении полупроводнико-
вых интегральных датчиков механичес-
ких величин. Целью изобретения являет-
ся повышение точности изготовления по-
лупроводниковых чувствительных тензо-
элементов с заданными градуировочными
характеристиками за счет выбора
одного из тензоэлементов в качестве
контрольного и измерения его выход-
ного параметра. Для измерения вы-
ходного параметра контрольного тен-
зоэлемента 4 устанавливают подклю-
чку на подставку 5 и нагружают ее
в зоне расположения контрольного
тензоэлемента 4 постоянной механичес-
кой нагрузкой. Для этого в процессе
травления устраивают паузы. 2 з.п.
ф-лы, 1 ил.